

Deliverable D4

Summary report on impedance-based measurement results of cells and modules during LCTs under various cycling conditions, such as cell geometry, cell energy, charging and temperature conditions

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Deliverable D4 of the EMPIR – Project 17IND10 “LiBforSecUse”

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 Introduction	4
2 Life Cycle Tests (LCTs) on Reference Cells	5
2.1 Inter-lab comparison	5
2.1.1 Measured capacity (SoH) evolution and GEIS data sets.....	6
2.1.2 Finding correlations between the EIS response of a battery and its SoH	7
2.1.3 Repeatability (reproducibility) of SoH-EIS evolution.....	11
2.1.4 Repeatability (reproducibility) of NFRA in the Inter-lab comparison task	13
2.2 Calendar aging tests	17
2.3 Effect of Temperature and DoD range during cycling.....	20
2.3.1 Effect of Temperature on full DoD range cycling	20
2.3.2 Effect of used DoD range during cycling	25
3 Life Cycle Tests on Additional Cells.....	30
3.1 Alternative high-energy batteries	30
3.2 Modules.....	32
3.3 Other batteries	33
3.3.1 Extending the lower cut-off voltage down to 2.5 V	33
3.3.2 Cylindrical LFP-Graphite battery.....	34
4 Summary and outlook	36
4.1 Summary.....	36
4.2 Conclusions and outlook	38

Abbreviations

EIS – Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

NFRA – Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis

LCT – Life Cycle Test

EoL – End of Life (of a battery cell)

SoH – State of Health (of a battery cell)

Ni-rich NMC - Layered Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt oxide with high content of Nickel

LFP – Lithium iron phosphate

GEIS – Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy with current perturbation signal

DC – Direct Current

SoC – State of Charge (of a battery cell)

CC discharge – Constant Current (galvanostatic) discharge

CC-CV charge – Constant Current (galvanostatic) charge followed by an additional Constant Voltage charge [until specified current limit]

SEI – Solid Electrolyte Interface

PE – periodic evaluation

Re(Z) – Real part of impedance

Im(Z) – Imaginary part of impedance

|Z| – Impedance magnitude

FEC – full equivalent cycle

1 Introduction

The European EMPIR project 17IND10 [1] aims to provide a metrological approach to characterize Lithium-ion batteries that have completed their first industrial life in electric vehicles and can be used for a second application, for example as a stationary energy storage system. For this purpose, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was applied in WP2 as the main non-destructive (and *in-situ*) technique for accessing of the internal state of the tested battery cells and modules (A2.3.2). Additionally, in the sets of tests conducted by KIT partner a second *in-situ* nonlinear technique was applied – Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis (NFRA, A2.3.3). In order to mimic a transition “from first to second life” of a battery cell in real application, an appropriate (realistic) charge/discharge procedure needs to be performed. Moreover, aging at elevated temperature can provide further information regarding the aspects of battery degradation during long-lasting (passive) storage period(s). For use of batteries in electric vehicles an End of Life (EoL) of a battery is typically considered to take place when State of Health (SOH) decreases down to 80% relatively to an initial state (i.e., capacity reaches 80% of the initial or nominal capacity value). In realistic conditions of Li-ion battery usage this represents a long-term cycling period with typically an order of 1000 cycles to be performed. In most of the cycling tests done in the LiBforSecUse project we used high-energy cells that are comparable (by nature of active materials in the electrodes) to those being built-in into modern battery modules/packs for automotive applications. Specifically, the batteries included a Ni-rich NMC cathode (with a chemical composition close to Ni : Mn : Co = 8:1:1) and a Graphite anode material with low addition of silicon (Si) particles in order to increase the initial capacity of a cell. For more detailed specifications of the active materials and electrodes please see the report of Activity 2.4.3 and 2.4.4. For comparison some tests were performed on batteries with other chemistry (LFP-Graphite).

During the initial long-term cycling period, as well as in the following cycling period beyond the EoL, EIS spectra were systematically periodically measured by applying current-controlled impedance (GEIS). In the same manner NFRA were also recorded only for the LCT that were performed at KIT. Within WP2 several selected commercial Lithium-ion battery cells and one battery module were methodically tested by performing charge-discharge cycling procedures (i.e., Life Cycle Test (LCT) protocols) at determined controlled conditions (temperature, current, voltage window, DOD range). For more details about the measurement conditions of the LCTs please see deliverable D3. On a selected battery cell type (reference cell) also calendar aging tests at defined SoC and temperature were conducted. The list of all initially planned and finally conducted tests together with the testing conditions applied are presented in the table in **Appendix-I**.

For both types of experiments the cells were mounted in a measurement setup that enables 4-point-contact electrochemical measurements (for details see D3). For all the LCTs as well as the calendar aging tests the GEIS responses and the measurements for NFRA were performed at 23°C. GEIS responses were measured at 0.5 A from 10^{-2} - 10^4 Hz. Meanwhile, NFR measurements were performed at higher excitation amplitude, i.e., 5 A, and smaller frequency range, 10^{-1} – 10^3 Hz. The lower bound of the frequency range for NFR measurement is intended to be selected at 10^{-1} Hz, higher than GEIS, to avoid long measurement time, so that drifting in the cell state during measurement with high excitation amplitude can be avoided. Meanwhile, due to the limitation of the hardware devices, the interpretation of the NFR signals is limited up to 10^3 Hz. Obtained measurement results of the systematic cycling (and aging) tests with periodic GEIS/NFRA measurements of the tested cells are presented and described in the following sections 2 and 3.

2 Life Cycle Tests (LCTs) on Reference Cells

- Reference cells were commercial, nominally identical, high-energy, cylindrical NMC-Graphite 18650 batteries from the same production batch (procured and distributed by Aceleron). The reference cells were used for performing several experimental tasks: Inter-lab comparison;
- Checking of effect of Temperature and DoD range during cycling;
- Aging under calendar conditions;
- Additional LCTs performed at other cycling conditions.

In the following the listed individual tasks are explained in more detail and the main results and observations with discussion are provided.

2.1 Inter-lab comparison

Within the part of WP2 dedicated to the electrochemical measurements (cycling, GEIS) on reference cells an important emphasis was given to repeatability (reproducibility) of the electrochemical tests. It is important to stress that properties/performance of battery cells in general are affected by various factors. Even the conditions before the first battery usage (for example the previous warehouse storage temperature) in addition to the starting industrial production variance between the cells can somewhat affect the cell performance [2]. The inter-lab comparison between 6 partners was conducted on reference cells by performing LCTs with the same experimental conditions – but at different institutions and with different measurement equipment as listed in **Table 1**. Within the inter-lab comparison, the selected LCTs on 15 cylindrical LG18650 cells were performed by the 6 partners.

Table 1. Measurement equipment, number of cells and cell codes for the LCTs done for the Interlab comparison task.

Partner	Measurement equipment	Number of cells	Cell code (identifier)
PTB	Cycling: BasyTec XCTS EIS: Gamry Reference 3000 Multiplexer: BasyTec EIS Mux Climate chamber: Vötsch VT3 4060	4	PTB-15 PTB-16 PTB-17 PTB-18
JRC	Cycling: Maccor Series 4000 coupled with Modulab XM ECS (Solatron Analytical) for EIS Climatic chamber: BiA MTH 4.46	3	JRC-04 JRC-05 JRC-06
NPL	Cycling: BioLogic VMP3/VMP3-B10 EIS: BioLogic VMP3/VMP3-B10 Climatic chamber: Binder MK115 & ED56	2	NPL-11 NPL-12
KIT	Cycling: BasyTec XCTS, EIS: Zahner Zennium, NFRA: Zahner Zennium + Zahner PP241 Climate chamber: Weiss WK3-340/70	2	KIT-06 KIT-07
NIC	Cycling: BioLogic MPG-205, EIS: BioLogic SP-200 Climatic chamber: Binder KB 240	2	NIC-01 NIC-02
Aalto	Cycling: Maccor series 4300 EIS: BioLogic MPG-205, Climatic chamber: Vötsch VC3 4018	2	Aalto-03 Aalto-04

2.1.1 Measured capacity (SoH) evolution and GEIS data sets

In order to check general repeatability of the electrochemical cycling tests together with the corresponding impedance measurements, a comparative analysis of the obtained data for the 15 selected cells (**Table 1**) was performed. Firstly, the dependence of SoH vs. cycle number of the cells (**Fig. 1**) was compared with each other in order to observe general trends and deviations.

Fig. 1. Evolution of SoH of the 15 reference cells during the LCTs for the Inter-lab comparison task.

The main general trend observed for all of the cells is the rather fast decrease of SoH in the initial stage of cycling (typically during about 200 cycles) which is probably linked with the fast degradation of performance of Si particles in the anode. In the following (second) stage one observes a close-to-linear decrease of SoH with cycle number, $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$. The latter rate of SoH decrease is observed to be quite comparable for most of the cells which is found to be about -1% per 100 cycles. The largest deviation from these trends is observed for the two cells tested at NPL. A possible reason could lie in the calendar aging effect that these two tests started significantly later (about 1 year) than the others due to Covid-19 related restrictions. In addition, these two cells might have aged more when the LCT was terminated at late night, weekend or holidays then cells were stored longer at the elevated temperature of 45°C than the design of experiment which ideally requires that the cells transfer promptly to the ambient 23°C climatic chamber for the periodic health check point. On the other hand, all the cells tested at PTB show a comparable second-stage “linear” decrease of SoH (i.e. the same value of $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$) as the other cells. At the same time, it seems that their measured SoH is somewhat larger compared to the cells tested at the other institutions. In the third stage a transition to more rapid decrease of SoC (a higher value of $-\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$) is observed. The evolution of SoH in this third stage of testing was found to be the least reproducible, that is, it depended the most on individual properties of cells. For example, one of the cells tested at PTB (PTB-17) exhibited this third stage already before ca. 1500 cycles while the other three cells continued the linear (second) stage of SoH decrease beyond 2000 cycles.

The onset of the third stage and further SoH (capacity) evolution is very important for the second-life use of a battery cell. The possibility of prediction of this onset would be of major importance, especially as in some cases an accelerated decrease of battery SoH was observed. Here, it is important to note that the conditions during the Inter-lab comparison LCTs were quite harsh (charging with a maximal recommended current of 1.33C, and at the elevated temperature of 45°C). Consequently, the observed evolutions of SoH showed a relatively short cycle life (1200 – 1800 cycles) when reaching the EoL condition. In real applications standard Li-ion battery cells (with standard electrolytes) are almost never exposed to such constant elevated temperatures. Accordingly, the SoH evolutions obtained in the Interlab comparison task (**Fig. 1**) should be considered as the results of slightly accelerated degradation tests. This was done due to the limited project duration within which we not only wanted to reach EoL of a battery but also to obtain the evolution of SoH beyond EoL, thus covering effectively the actual “second life” of a battery.

The periodic measurements of EIS and NFRA determination for the Inter-lab comparison task produced a large data set with more than 5000 EIS spectra and around 300 NFR spectra obtained. For that reason only part of the data is shown in the present report for the selected SoC = 100% as presented in the **Appendix II**. The sets of EIS spectra measured at other SoCs exhibit comparable information and are thus not shown in the report. Most importantly, already a fast checking of the data demonstrates that there was a natural spread in EIS of the cells with slightly different initial SoH evolution and furthermore the data sets varied more significantly between the partners in the SoH at the end of tests. Because of those two reasons the EIS data sets needed to be compared using a simplified approach as described in continuation.

2.1.2 Finding correlations between the EIS response of a battery and its SoH

For the purpose of being able to estimate the repeatability of the evolution of the sets of measured impedance spectra during the long-term LCTs (**Fig. 1**), a proper correlation between the EIS spectrum and SoH of the cell had to be found. The procedure of finding of such a correlation is demonstrated on typical examples of measurements obtained at NIC (LCT 1.05). **Fig. 2** shows the evolution of SoH of two cells (NIC-01 and NIC-02) as a function of cycle number. In **Fig. 3** the corresponding set of the EIS spectra measured on cell NIC-01 at several SoCs is presented.

Fig. 2. Typical example of evolution of SoH of the reference cells during 4 A cycling at 45°C in full DoD range and CV step at the upper cut off voltage (Interlab comparison test LCT 1.05, NIC-01 and NIC-02) as a function of cycle number.

Fig. 3. Typical measured set of the EIS spectra obtained in the Inter-lab comparison tests. Presented are the results of LCT 1.05 for cell NIC-01 obtained at SoC: a) 100 %, b) 65 %, c) 50 %, and d) 20 %. In the legends the cycle numbers at which the particular EIS spectrum was measured are shown.

It can be observed in **Fig. 3** that, at all SoCs the EIS spectra show a gradual increase of impedance values with increasing cycle number. Furthermore, it can be seen that the impedances at the same cycle number are the largest at SoC = 100 % and gradually became smaller with reducing SoC down to 20 %. At all the SoCs a gradual increase in the high-frequency intercept and interfacial impedance arc can be seen. Moreover, the increase (increment) of the interfacial impedance arc prevails over the increase of the high-frequency intercept; and this effect is the strongest at the highest SoC. Plainly such a direct comparison of the EIS spectra gives some information, but it does not provide any further direct insight into the corresponding SoH evolution of the compared cells. Obviously, the SoH evolution and related impedance responses need to be represented in such a way that a direct SoH-EIS correlation could be plotted. One of the simplest possibilities to do so is presented in **Fig. 4**, and is based on the so-called *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption*, as explained in continuation.

Instead of applying elaborated analysis techniques for disentangling the impedance data and relating them to the output of the SoH evolution, we here proceed with a simple approach. This simplification is particularly justified due to the very large amount of the EIS data and, additionally, due to the fact that some spectra exhibit peculiar trends. Thus, the so-called *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption* is presented in **Fig. 4** where 3 typical EIS spectra from a set of Inter-lab comparison LCTs is shown (specifically, NIC-0001 in **Fig. 3**). We assume that the impedance response obtained at the lowest measured frequency (f_{min}) includes – from the point of view of impedance magnitude - all the contributions measured down to that frequency. In other words, when attempting to relate the results of galvanostatic cycling (e.g. discharge capacity or equivalently SoH evolution) with a magnitude of impedance at a single measured frequency, the lower the frequency the more reasonable is to expect that a reasonable correlation could be found. The latter reasoning is based on the practical experimental fact that the important diffusional contributions in Li-ion insertion systems (both in liquid electrolyte phase and in the bulk of solid state) are observed at low frequencies. For example, in the case of 811 NMC cathodes the diffusional processes are typically observed in ranges between 50 mHz down to 1 mHz [3, 4, 5]. In fact, the impedance response of the solid-state diffusion resistance contribution of 811 NMC was found to be extending below 1 mHz [3].

Here it is needed to note that one important practical restriction has to be satisfied: f_{min} must be lower than the transition from the interfacial to diffusional part of a battery cell impedance spectrum. According to the previous work on 811 NMC based cathodes f_{min} for this particular cathode was found to be around 50 mHz [3]. Preliminary results on graphite anode are indicating that f_{min} is found roughly around 100 mHz. Accordingly, it is reasonable to assume that in the case of 811 NMC-Graphite battery cells the f_{min} will typically be larger than 10 mHz. A simple observation of the spectra in **Fig. 4** shows that this is definitely true for a pristine cell while in the case of considerably degraded cells f_{min} gradually reduces to get closer to 10 mHz. Thus, it seems that the sets of EIS spectra with $f_{min} = 10$ mHz could be expected to exhibit some reasonable correlation with SoH – at least in the cases when severe degradation of the interfaces has not yet taken place.

Fig. 4. Representation of the *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption* shown for the case of three typical EIS spectra from a set of measured EIS data in the Inter-lab comparison LCT (shown is an example of cell NIC-01 from **Fig. 3a** for SoC = 100 % after 500, 2000 and 3200 cycles).

In **Fig. 5** an example of NIC-0001 cell impedance evolution is represented where the real ($Re(Z)$) and imaginary parts ($-Im(Z)$) of impedance at selected $f_{min} = 10$ mHz are plotted as functions of cycle number for various SoC's. It is clearly seen in **Fig. 5** that $Re(Z)$ shows a monotone increase with increasing cycle number for all the SoC's, while $-Im(Z)$ mostly increases with some slight fluctuations

(and experimental scattering). Furthermore, it can be clearly seen that the set of data obtained at SoC = 100% exhibits the largest absolute values.

Fig. 5. Example of sets of NIC-0001 cell EIS evolution at selected $f_{min} = 10$ mHz showing dependence of the components $\text{Re}(Z)$ and $-\text{Im}(Z)$ as a function of cycle number during the corresponding LCT (1.05).

In **Fig. 6** the chosen example of NIC-0001 cell impedance evolution is shown as a correlation between the real and imaginary components of EIS and the corresponding SoH (SoH-EIS correlation) for $f_{min} = 10$ mHz and various SoCs. It can be deduced from **Fig. 6** that for the both relations (with $\text{Re}(Z)$ and with $-\text{Im}(Z)$) the dependence at SoC = 100% clearly deviates from the behaviour at other SoCs.

Fig. 6. Example of sets of NIC-0001 cell EIS evolution at selected $f_{min} = 10$ mHz showing the dependence of components $\text{Re}(Z)$ and $-\text{Im}(Z)$ as a function of cycle number during the corresponding LCT (1.05).

In principle, any of the SoC sets could be used for the repeatability analysis, but since it seems that the set obtained at SoC = 100% shows some regions with a linear SoH-EIS dependence (**Fig. 7**), we decided to use this particular condition (SoC = 100%) in the present analysis.

a) b)

Fig. 7. Selected set of SoH-EIS evolution shown for an example of cell NIC-0001 obtained for $f_{min} = 10$ mHz and SoC = 100%. Correlation of SoH with the corresponding impedance is shown for: a) $\text{Re}(Z)$, and b) $-\text{Im}(Z)$.

2.1.3 Repeatability (reproducibility) of SoH-EIS evolution

The methodology of simple analysis of EIS evolution based on the *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption* was applied to the results of Inter-lab comparison LCTs (see **Table 1**) for the case of sets obtained at SoC = 100%. **Fig. 8** shows the obtained results of the experimental correlation SoH-EIS where on x-axis the values of impedance magnitude ($|Z|$) for EIS measurements at $f_{min} = 10$ mHz are plotted. At first glance, the SoH-EIS dependence shown in **Fig. 8** is very much resembling the SoH dependence upon cycle number (**Fig. 1**) so that the resemblance of the two relations is also expected. Even more, the general observation of the similarity of the relations gives a strong direct support to the main aim of this project – it clearly proves that impedance can be used as a tool to directly track SoH of a Li-ion battery cell during its life time.

A more detailed comparison of the relations in **Fig. 1** and **Fig. 8** (as well as **Fig. 9**) reveals that during the initial stage of cycling (with probable degradation of Si in the anode being the main mechanism) is also directly reflected in the SoH- $|Z|$ relation. It seems that the probable initial degradation of Si in the anode (resulting in the rather rapid loss of capacity in the initial ~ 200 cycles) does not produce more rapid increase of impedance ($|Z|$) at 10 mHz for SoC = 100%. In other words, $|Z|$ at 10 mHz for SoC = 100% seems not to be directly sensitive to the degradation of Si particles. This observation is not surprising since both NMC cathode and Graphite anode exhibit a strong dependence of EIS upon SoC. For example, already the relations in **Fig. 6** are indicating that the initial SoH evolution might be more directly correlated with impedance response obtained at lower SoCs.

Fig. 8. Obtained SoH-EIS dependence for the Inter-lab comparison task where SoH is plotted as a function of impedance magnitude ($|Z|$) for EIS spectra measured at $f_{min} = 10$ mHz and SoC = 100%.

Fig. 9 shows a magnification of the initial stage and the second stage of cycling. In the latter it is observed that the close-to-linear rate of SoH decrease with cycle number is aligned with a close-to-linear rate of SoH decrease with increase in impedance magnitude, $|Z|$, as clearly seen in **Fig. 9**. Accordingly, we can relate the observed $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$ rate with $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$ rate. For the compared cells in the SoH range between 0.7 and ~ 0.9 the average $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$ decrease is found to be about -0.17% per 1 m Ω . By comparing the two rates ($\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$ and $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$) we find that the cell in the Interlab comparison task showed in the second stage of cycling in average about 6 m Ω increase in $|Z|$ per 100 cycles (for the selected SoC = 100%). The results obtained at NPL clearly deviate from this relation similarly as already described above for the dependency of SoH with cycle number. We attribute the reasons for this deviation to the same fact – namely that the tests at NPL started later than the other tests with about 1 year delay (due to Covid-19 related restrictions) including additional temperature effect aforementioned which probably resulted in somewhat worse initial condition of the two cells.

Fig. 9. Part of the SoH-EIS dependence for the Interlab comparison task (zoom-in of Fig. 8) that includes the first and the second stage of cycling. SoH is plotted as a function of impedance magnitude ($|Z|$) for EIS spectra measured at $f_{min} = 10$ mHz and SoC = 100%.

In the third stage of testing (in most of the cases below SoH = 0.7) the cells exhibited the individual-cell-dependent evolutions. Practically for all of the cells in the third stage the rate of SoH decrease (i.e. the value of $-\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$) became larger compared to the second stage. Regarding the second use (“life”) of a Li ion battery, it can be speculated that a reliable determination of $-\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$ could play an important role in estimation of practical useful remaining life of a battery cell.

2.1.4 Repeatability (reproducibility) of NFRA in the Inter-lab comparison task

An inter-lab comparison could not be carried out for the NFRA measurements since KIT is the only institution that had carried out these measurements. However, the reproducibility of this method can be compared on two cells: KIT-06 and KIT-07. These two cells had been aged under the same conditions (DoD = 0 - 100% and 45 °C) and we see in **Fig. 10** that the aging progression in both cells are very similar. The nonlinearities of the cells are analyzed based on the second (Y_2) and third (Y_3) harmonic signals. Unlike the EIS measurements, where the spectra at SoC 100% were analyzed, the analysis for NFR was carried out on at SoC 80%, 65%, 50%, 35% and 20%. The NFRA was not recorded at SoC 100% in order to avoid a drift in the system due to the high excitation amplitude of 5 A.

Fig. 10. Aging progression of KIT-06 and KIT-07. Both cells were aged under the same conditions of: DoD = 100% and at 45°C

Fig. 11. Impedance (a) and NFRA (b) of KIT-06 from LCT 1.05. Simultaneous increase in impedance and nonlinearities with increasing cycle numbers.

In **Fig. 11** we see that the increase in the nonlinear signals in the lower frequency range (< 2 Hz) can be well correlated to the increase in the impedance as shown in the semicircle at the lower frequency (1 – 10 Hz) in the impedance spectrum. This shows that the process that underlies in the frequency range is highly nonlinear and we attribute this nonlinear process as the charge transfer process at the electrode/electrolyte interface. As the cells age, the semicircle specifically at this frequency range increases significantly, so do the nonlinear signals that arise from this process. This signifies that not only the charge transfer process becomes more impeded (Y_3 increases) but also the symmetrical behaviour of the charge transfer process is violated (Y_2 increases) [6, 7].

Fig. 12. NFR spectra of KIT-06 at different SoCs that was measured at 5 A, 23°C and between 10^{-1} – 10^3 Hz.

Fig. 13. NFR spectra of KIT-07 at different SoCs that was measured at 5 A, 23°C and between 10^{-1} – 10^3 Hz.

This similar aging behaviour with increasing Y_2 and Y_3 can be observed at other SoCs (**Fig. 12** and **Fig. 13**). However, the nonlinear signals seem to be stronger at high SoC and at low frequency and this SoCs dependency is in consistent with the impedance spectra as shown in **Fig. 3**. With this in mind, we have selected 0.1 Hz at SoC 80% for the subsequent analysis.

Looking at **Fig. 10** and **Fig. 11(b)**, we can see that the constant increase in nonlinear signals Y_2 and Y_3 correlates well to a SoH decrease. With this NFRA method, we are also able to distinguish the three different stages of aging by analyzing the quotient of the nonlinear signals Y_3/Y_2 (see **Fig. 15**). The results obtained are very much comparable to the EIS technique shown in **Fig. 8**. During the first stage of aging, we have a decrease in the Y_3/Y_2 , which means that the increase in Y_2 is greater than Y_3 in this stage. One reason for the great increase in Y_2 could be the increased overpotential in diffusion process, which resulted in greater asymmetry of this process [7]. In the second stage, where we have a linear SoH decrease, the increase in Y_3 surpassed Y_2 . This indicates that the kinetic of the charge transfer process decreases, possibly due to the loss of active material or inhibition of the active surface area on the electrode [8]. In stage three, again we have a decrease in the Y_3/Y_2 . This is

possibly due to the transition from symmetrical to asymmetrical charge transfer process. On the whole, we can say that NFR results on both cells are very similar and the analysis based on the Y_2 and Y_3 signals can deliver good reproducibility.

Fig. 14. Three stages of aging can be distinguished by analyzing the quotient of Y_3 to Y_2 signal (SoC 80%, 0.1 Hz). The value of Y_3/Y_2 (in b) can be correlated to the SOH progression (in a).

2.2 Calendar aging tests

Calendar aging tests were essentially tests where selected Li-ion battery cell (cylindrical 18650 NMC-Graphite) was held at controlled elevated temperature (45 °C) during a period of several months (up to 16 months in the case of tests conducted at KIT). During the aging period the cells were kept at the pre-defined SoC of: 100% (2 cells at PTB), 80% (2 cells at JRC), and 50% (2 cells at KIT). EIS responses of the cells were periodically measured in a chamber with controlled temperature at 23 °C. EIS measurements at PTB and JRC were performed with an interval of one month, while at KIT the EIS spectra were measured more frequently in order to gain more precise evolution of the impedance. The obtained EIS spectra are collected in **Appendix-III**. A typical example of the set of EIS spectra obtained during aging test performed at SoC = 50 % (cell KIT-09) is shown in **Fig. 15**. In the legend the time (number of days) passed since the start of the test is indicated. In **Fig. 15** it can be seen that during the aging there was slow increase in the high-frequency intercept. At the same time, an even more pronounced increase of the interfacial resistance (the size of the high-frequency arc(s)) can be observed. Thus it can be observed that this latter part of impedance increase contributes the most to the total increase of impedance at 10 mHz. Moreover, it can be clearly deduced that there was very small increase of $\text{Im}(Z)$ during the aging.

Fig. 15. Typical set of measured EIS evolution during calendaric aging test performed at SoC = 50 % and temperature of 45 °C. The data were obtained at KIT within the LCT 1.09 (cell KIT-09) where cells were aged for about 16 months (legend shows the duration of aging in days).

In **Fig. 16** a typical example of the time evolution EIS spectra obtained during aging test performed at SoC = 80 % (cell JRC-16) is shown. The particular spectra were measured at SoC = 100 %, the legend shows the duration of the aging test in months. When comparing the impedance spectra during aging at SoC = 80 % (**Fig. 16**) and at SoC = 50 % (**Fig. 15**), several differences can be observed. Firstly, aging at SoC = 80 % increases the rate of the high-frequency intercept growth. Secondly, aging at SoC = 80 % strongly accelerates the growth of the magnitude of interfacial resistance – observed as partial splitting of the high-frequency arc into two distinct impedance arcs. It appears that only the second arc (with a peak frequency of about 2 Hz) is increasing in size while the first one (with a peak frequency of about 160 Hz) remains rather unaltered. The magnitude of $\text{Im}(Z)$ during the aging at SoC = 80 % did not show any particular trend (in average it was practically constant). Again, the dominating effect to the total increase of impedance at f_{min} (10 mHz) during the aging at SoC = 80 % was the increase of the interfacial impedance (resistance).

Fig. 16. Typical set of measured EIS evolution during calendaric aging test performed at SoC = 80 % and temperature of 45 °C. The data were obtained at JRC within the LCT 1.08 (cell JRC-16) where cells were aged for 7 months (the legend shows aging period in months). The shown set of EIS spectra was measured at SoC = 100 %.

A comparison of typical evolutions of the impedance magnitude $|Z|$ at 10 mHz as a function of time for several tested cells is shown in **Fig. 17**. It can be seen that in general for all the cells the value of $|Z|(10 \text{ mHz})$ increases with time of aging. As already described above, the magnitude of impedance for this particular type of cell (reference cell) is the largest at SoC = 100 %. Accordingly, also the observed changes in the impedance magnitude are the largest at SoC = 100 %. The latter fact is clearly seen in **Fig. 17** where the rate of $|Z|$ increase grows from SoC = 50 %, 80 %, and is finally the largest at SoC = 100 %. Furthermore, it can be seen that for the same selected SoC = 50 % the time evolutions of the 2 cells aged at SoC = 80 % (JRC-15 and JRC-16) exhibit a slightly larger rate of $|Z|(10 \text{ mHz})$ increase compared to the cells aged at SoC = 50 % (KIT-08 and KIT-09).

From **Fig. 17** it is possible to read out the changes of impedance magnitude ($\Delta|Z|$) during the aging tests. The following trends are found: a) a 7.7 m Ω increase in the spectra measured at SoC = 100 % for the case of 7 months of aging at SoC = 80 % and b) a 4.6 m Ω increase in the spectra measured at SoC = 50 % for the case of 16 months of aging done at SoC = 50 %. It is possible to further compare these changes with the changes of impedance observed during cell cycling tests. From the comparison it can be found the following:

- a) The 7.7 m Ω increase (for EIS measured at SoC = 100 % and aging at 45 °C) corresponds to roughly 7 % of initial drop in SoH during cycling at 45 °C;
- b) The 4.6 m Ω increase (for EIS measured at SoC = 50 % and aging at 45 °C) corresponds to roughly 12 % of initial drop in SoH during cycling at 45 °C.

In other words, the increase $\Delta|Z|$ observed during aging of the cells at the elevated temperature of 45 °C would - in terms of an equal $\Delta|Z|$ increase during cycling - correspond to a very large decrease in the battery SoH. It would be interesting to perform tests (experiments) where these relations would be systematically experimentally verified.

Fig. 17. Typical evolution of IZI(10 mHz) as a function of time during the aging tests at 45 °C for several selected cells aged at: SoC = 80 % (JRC-15 and JRC-16) and SoC = 50 % (KIT-08 and KIT-09).

The aging tests performed at elevated temperature of 45 °C showed practically linear increase of impedance magnitude (at 10 mHz) with duration of aging. The aging of reference cells at SoC = 80 % was more severe compared to the aging at SoC = 50 %, with the aging at SoC = 80 % producing roughly “equivalent degradation” of 1 % of SoH loss per 1 month of aging (storage). The actual damage to the cells during the aging tests should be directly experimentally verified.

2.3 Effect of Temperature and DoD range during cycling

For the case of cylindrical LG18650 NMC-Graphite battery cells two additional types of systematic testing were conducted. In the first, the effect of the temperature during galvanostatic cycling at 1.33C (using standard procedure with CC-CV charge and CC discharge) was checked by performing tests at 35 °C, 23 °C, and 10 °C. In the second type of testing galvanostatic cycling at 1.33C was performed in several defined DoD ranges and at the selected temperature of 45 °C. During the cycling periodical measurements of EIS were conducted at selected predetermined SoCs.

2.3.1 Effect of Temperature on full DoD range cycling

The effect of temperature on battery SOH and the corresponding impedance evolution during long-term full DoD range cycling was checked by performing measurements at 3 institutions: JRC (at 35 °C, LCT 1.10), NIC (at 23 °C, LCT 1.13), and Aalto (at 10 °C, LCT 1.17). In **Fig. 18** the evolution of SoH of the cells with cycle number is shown. It appears that the two trends for the cells cycled at 35 °C and 23 °C cannot be distinguished. While on the other hand the cells cycled at Aalto at 10 °C show a strong deviation from that trend, with a very rapid decrease of SoH. Interestingly, it can be observed that for the cells cycled at 35 °C and 23 °C the rate of SoH decrease is reduced after passing the SoH =

60 % (corresponding to about 2800 cycles in average). This is quite important observation for the activities related with the second use (“life”) of Lithium ion batteries.

Fig. 18. Evolution of SoH of the 9 reference cells with cycle number where the effect of temperature during cycling was monitored.

In order to get a full insight into the actual effect of temperature during cycling, the data obtained in the tests conducted at 35 °C, 23 °C and 10 °C (**Fig. 18**) need to be compared with the data obtained at the elevated temperature of 45 °C (shown in **Fig. 1**). In fact, the latter are the very tests that were conducted during the Inter-lab comparison task. In **Fig. 19** we show all the 24 sets of SoH evolutions needed to perform an analysis of SoH-EIS correlations obtained during cycling at different temperatures. In **Fig. 20** it can be seen that some of the cells cycled at 35 °C and 23 °C tend to show somewhat extended cycle life (when reaching SoH = 80 %) compared to the cells cycled at 45 °C. On the other hand, the two cells cycled at Aalto at 10 °C clearly show a strong deviation of the SoH trend with observed extremely fast degradation of capacity.

Fig. 19. All the sets of data needed to perform analysis of the effect of temperature during cycling on the evolution of the SoH-EIS correlation.

Overall, an analysis of the SoH-Cycle trends shown in **Fig. 19** and **Fig. 20** suggests a rather difficult decoupling of the effects of temperature during cycling on one hand and cell-to-cell variations between the individual cells on the other (exception being cells cycled at 10 °C). In other words, additional parameters are needed to give us enough information to be able to differentiate between the various degradation modes going on in the cells. For this purpose, the methodology of analysis of impedance evolution based on the *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption* was applied.

In **Appendix-IV** we present the corresponding sets of EIS spectra measured periodically during the cycling. Again, due to the large amount of data, only spectra measured at SoC = 100 % are shown. It is interesting to note that, for example, in the two tests conducted at JRC (JRC-10 and JRC-11) there were about 100 impedance spectra measured for each cell during the LCT. An example of evolution of the measured EIS spectra during cycling at 35 °C is shown in **Fig. 21** (cell JRC-11). In the following we present results of SoH-EIS correlation analysis for all the 24 cells included in the analysis of the effect of temperature on the cycling evolution.

Fig. 20. All the sets of data needed to perform an analysis of the effect of temperature during cycling on the evolution of the SoH-EIS correlation (magnified part of Fig. 19 at higher SoH).

Fig. 21. Example of evolution of EIS during full DoD range cycling of reference cylindrical LG18650 cell at 35 °C conducted at JRC. The EIS data were measured at 23 °C. The cell used was JRC-11.

In **Fig. 22** we show the results of the SoH-EIS correlation analysis for all of the 24 tested cells that were used for monitoring of the effect of temperature on the cycling evolution. It can be clearly seen in **Fig. 22** that the groups of cells cycled at different temperatures are definitely separated in the rate of SoH decrease with increasing IZI(10 mHz). This is a very important observation since it directly supports the validity of the correlation analysis methodology based on the *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption*. Moreover, it provides additional insights into the degradation mechanisms going on in this type of battery cells. Namely, in **Fig. 22** it can be clearly seen that there is a definite trend of SoH with the cycling temperature: the lower the temperature the larger is the rate of the capacity decrease. Moreover, in some ranges the SoH-IZI dependencies are rather close to linear. This fact gives a direct affirmation that impedance-based techniques could indeed be used for monitoring and possibly even predicting of the future SoH evolution in the second use (“life”) of Lithium ion batteries.

From the variation of the evolution of SoH-IZI relations with temperature shown in **Fig. 22** it can be reasoned that lowering of temperature is extremely detrimental for this particular cell - possibly due to strongly enhanced metal Lithium plating on the anode particles during (relatively) large charging current ($4 \text{ A} \cong 1.33 \text{ C}$ rate). The latter reasoning further suggests that, for this particular cell, at temperatures below $35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the cycle life is probably strongly affected by the dominant mechanism of solid electrolyte interface (SEI) degradation on graphite anode (and other related effects) as a consequence of Lithium metal plating.

Fig. 22. Sets of SoH-IZI correlations for the groups of reference cells cycled at different temperatures. The impedance magnitudes IZI were collected at $f_{min} = 10 \text{ mHz}$ for the spectra measured at SoC = 100 %.

Furthermore, from the comparison of **Fig. 20** and **Fig. 23** it can be deduced that the degradation damage developed during cycling at $35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is less pronouncedly observed in EIS spectra in frequency range until 10 mHz . And oppositely, the degradation processes at the elevated temperature of $45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lead to a relatively larger impedance (IZI) increase at 10 mHz compared to

cycling at lower temperatures. The reason for this observation could probably be found by further studying the trends and analyzing the EIS spectra in such a way that it would be possible to attribute the actual physical phenomena to the impedance features.

Fig. 23. Sets of SoH-IZI correlations for the groups of reference cells cycled at different temperatures. Enlarged part of Fig. 22 at higher SoH showing 1st and 2nd stage of cycling.

2.3.2 Effect of used DoD range during cycling

The effect of used DoD range on battery SoH and the corresponding impedance evolution during long-term cycling at the selected temperature of 45 °C was checked by performing measurements at 4 institutions: JRC (LCT 1.11 DoD = 25-75), NIC (LCT 1.12 DoD = 50-100), NPL (LCT 1.14 DoD = 0-50), KIT (LCT 1.15 DoD = 30-100 and DoD = 10-80, LCT 1.16 DoD = 60-90 and DoD = 25-55). We define here full equivalent cycle (FEC) by simply normalizing the cycle number (N) by a factor F that represents the fraction of the full DoD range used during cycling:

$$FEC = N \times F = N \times \frac{\Delta DoD}{100} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

In **Fig. 24** we show the evolution of SoH of the cells with FEC. It appears that the cells tested at NIC have better stability compared to other cells. This is partially due to the real effect of the testing conditions where by applying DoD in the range of 50-100 one avoids the degradation processes at high-voltages. In addition to that, the periodic evaluation (PE) done at NIC was conducted at a lower current (0.5 A = C/6 C-rate) compared to the other partners (1.25 A). Consequently, the SoH values obtained at NIC are more stable (dropping slower) compared to the tests done at the other partners.

Fig. 24. Evolution of SoH with FEC of the 13 reference cells where the effect of DoD range during cycling was monitored.

In order to perform a full comparison of the effect of DoD range on SoH and the related impedance evolution, also the results obtained with the cells from Inter-lab comparison task should be included. In **Fig. 25** SoH evolution of four selected (representative) cells from Inter-lab comparison are added (black lines). It can be seen in **Fig. 25** and **Fig. 26** that the cycling stability of cells from the Inter-lab comparison (DOD = 0-100 %) is the worst of all the tested DoD ranges (only exception being cell KIT-10). And this trend is observed already from the beginning in the 1st stage of cycling (**Fig. 26**). Interestingly, the KIT cells (KIT-11 and KIT-13) that were cycled in the central part of DoD range with small DoD span ($\Delta\text{DoD} = 30\%$) seem to be showing the best stability with FEC. On the other hand, the cells tested at JRC (JRC-13, JRC-17, JRC-19) were cycled in the central DoD range as well – but the DoD span was larger ($\Delta\text{DoD} = 50\%$). This observation is suggesting that small DoD span might be favorable for long-term cycling stability. Of course, it is questionable how practical would this kind of cycling be for real-use applications.

Fig. 25. Evolution of SoH with FEC of the reference cells where the effect of DoD range during cycling was monitored (black lines correspond to 4 cells from Inter-lab comparison task).

The most stable SoH evolution in the 1st stage (Fig. 26) was observed for the cells cycled at NPL (DoD = 0-50 %) but are latter on at about 1000 FECs surpassed by the mentioned two KIT cells with narrow DoD span of cycling (KIT-11 and KIT-13). It is important to note that the cells from Inter-lab comparison are the only cells that were cycled in full DoD range, while all the other cells were cycled in partial ranges. It appears that for obtaining more insight about the long-term cycling stability larger number of cells should be tested at the same testing condition. The latter would help to identify the “outliers” and enable selecting the cells that show repeatable behaviour – thus effectively reducing the effect of cell-to-cell variations (at the same testing condition).

Fig. 26. Enlarged 1st stage of evolution of SoH with FEC of the reference cells where the effect of DoD range during cycling was monitored (black lines correspond to 4 cells from Interlab comparison task).

During the cycling of the cells in different DoD ranges periodic measurements of EIS responses were conducted, as shown in **Appendix-V** for the case of SoC = 50 %. In **Fig. 27** and **Fig. 28** we show sets of obtained SoH-IZI correlations for 10 mHz at SoC = 50 %. Overall, the trends seem to be rather comparable. The evolutions for the cells tested at NIC seem to somehow deviate, the reason for the latter fact is not clear. It interesting to observe that the cell KIT-10 that was found to deviate from other cells with partial DoD cycling ranges also deviates in the corresponding SoH-IZI correlations. Namely, it appears to follow trend that is non-distinguishable from the full DoD range cycling results.

From the data shown in **Fig. 27** and **Fig. 28** it is not possible to unambiguously extract definite conclusions regarding the most preferred DoD range to achieve stable long term cycling. Moreover, it is not straightforward to obtain clear reasoning about the observed trends in the SoH-IZI correlations. Partially this is due to the fact that effect of DoD cycling range on stability is rather complex and furthermore it is in the experiments additionally blurred by the individual cell-to-cell variations. As mentioned above – larger number of cells should be tested at the same testing condition. The latter would help to identify the “outliers” and enable selecting the group of cells that show repeatable behaviour.

Fig. 27. Sets of SoH-IZI correlations for the groups of reference cells cycled within different DoD ranges at 45 °C. The impedance magnitudes IZI were collected at $f_{min} = 10$ mHz for the spectra measured at SoC = 50 %.

Fig. 28. Enlarged part of Fig. 27 at high SoHs. Sets of SoH-IZI correlations for the groups of reference cells cycled within different DoD ranges at 45 °C. The impedance magnitudes IZI were collected at $f_{min} = 10$ mHz for the spectra measured at SoC = 50 %.

Apart from cell KIT-06 and KIT-07, NFR measurements were also carried out on 4 other cells that were aged at different conditions: KIT-10 (DoD: 30-100), KIT-11 (DoD: 60-90), KIT-12 (DoD: 10-80), KIT-13 (DoD: 25-55). The effect of DoD cycling range and the SoH-|Z| correlations have been discussed previously in Section 2.3.2. In this section, we shall look at the effect of DoD and cycling range on the NFRA results, along with the EIS.

[OBJ]

Fig. 29. NFR spectrum (left) and EIS (right) of cells measured at SoH 80 %, SoC 50 % and 23°C. Impact of difference in DoD can be observed in the spectra. Cell KIT-06 and KIT-07 have a DoD of 100 %, whereas DoD of KIT-10 and KIT-12 is 70 %.

The impact of DoD can be observed in Fig. 29. Although all four cells had been aged to SoH 80%, however their EIS and NFR spectra showed different development. In comparison to KIT-10 and KIT-12, which have a cycle depth of 70 %, KIT-06 and KIT-07, which were cycled with a DoD of 100 % showed an overall higher Y_2 and Y_3 -signals in Region I, as well as a greater semicircle in the EIS in Region II.

Cycling at a larger DoD could result in greater volume changes in the silicon-graphitic anode due to the greater volume fraction of the de-/intercalated lithium ions. The continuous expansion and shrinkage of the anode induce mechanical stress within the active material particles, causing cracks on the electrode particle surface. The freshly generated surface area from the cracks that expose to the electrolyte will react with the electrolyte and form new SEI layer on the electrode surface [8]. On the cathodic side, the active material in cathode will experience greater extent of the phase transformations at larger DoD cycling (especially at higher value of upper cut-off voltage), which could cause transition metal dissolution into the electrolyte [8].

[OBJ]

Fig. 30. NFR spectra (in a, c) and EIS (in b, d) of cell KIT-10 (top) and KIT-12 (bottom) after different number of equivalent full cycles and the respective SoHs. The measurements were carried out at SoC 50% and 23°C.

Fig.31: NFR spectra (in a, c) and EIS (in b, d) of cell KIT-11 (top) and KIT-13 (bottom) after different number of equivalent full cycles and the respective SoHs. The measurements were carried out at SoC 50% and 23°C.

Despite being cycled with the same cycle depth, cell KIT-10 experienced accelerated degradation after 1000 equivalent full cycles. Aging in cell KIT-12 remained somewhat insignificant. As cell KIT-10 was generally cycled at higher voltage niveau than cell KIT-12, this promotes a greater extent of transition metal dissolution from the cathode side and leads to greater loss of active materials or capacity fade when compared to cell KIT-12. The dissolved transition metal will be then transported from the cathode to the anode side, which favours and accelerates the SEI growth. This results in a greater inhibition of the active surface area and thus, impedes the charge transfer process at the anode. Hence, greater nonlinear signals and impedance can be observed for cell KIT-10 as shown in **Fig. 30**.

In **Figs. 30Figb** and **30d**, we can see from impedance spectra that the ohmic resistance in cell KIT-10 increased significantly in comparison to KIT-12. This is because cycling at higher voltage niveau is always accompanied not only by the dissolution of the transition metal but also the electrolyte oxidization at the cathode side.

Likewise, the impact of cycling range can be observed in the EIS and NFR spectra (**Fig. 31**) of cell KIT-11 and KIT-13. Despite having the same cycle depth, the increased in nonlinearities signals, especially Y_2 in greater in cell KIT-13, which corresponds to the impedance increase of the charge-transfer reaction. Here, the results show that cell KIT-11 that was cycled at higher voltage niveau aged less significant than cell KIT-13, which is the reverse case for the previous scenario. This actually can be explained by the different intercalation stages at the graphitic anode. As reported in [9], there is no change in intercalation stage between DoD 30 % – 90 % as the anodic potential level is relative flat within this region while cycling between DoD 25 % -55 % could experience at least two intercalation stages, which could result in greater mechanical stress (eventually cracks) within the particles, forming new SEI layer and creating greater impedance for the charge transfer process.

3 Life Cycle Tests on Additional Cells

Life cycle test on high energy cells around 50 Ah and modules have been conducted. It has been the intention to apply the empirical models described in D5 to impedance spectra from LCTs of these batteries to validate the applicability of the methodologies to other types of battery cells, and to modules. Unfortunately, the delays imposed by the Covid-19 pandemic made it eventually impossible to evaluate the data adequately. Here, we just summarise the measurements briefly. The cell data have not been considered at all for further evaluation. A report on a preliminary, qualitative evaluation of the module data will be published at the LiBforSecUse repository at Zneodo.org.

3.1 Alternative high-energy batteries

Four commercial 50 Ah, NMC-Graphite, prismatic cells, 20 mm aluminum bracing from a Chinese manufacturer (P/N P140, Actia) have been measured under the following conditions:

capacity measurements	
current i_c / A	25 A and 2.5 A
number of refreshs prior to the meas.	1
temperature / °C	23°C
idle time after charge / min	0 min
lower cut-off voltage U_{cut} / V	3.3 V
current for SOC adjustment	25 A

impedance measurements	
EIS mode (galva/pot)	galva
f_{max} / Hz	6 kHz
f_{min} / Hz	0.01 Hz
measurement frequencies per decade	10
amplitude of current / A or voltage / V	5 A
direct current / A	0
Z_guess	
temperature / °C	23°C
SoCs	20%, 35%, 50%, 65%, 80%, 100%
Relaxation time after last operation	4h
Measurement interval	100
Total no of cycles	2100
End of test SOH	71 %

3.2 Modules

The cells described in 3.1 have been used to prepare 4 modules, each consisting of 5 cells connected in series. An individual module is shown below.

Each module had a nominal voltage of 18 V. Balancing units had been developed by PTB and added on top of each cell to prevent overcharging. Impedance spectra have been measured from the individual cells of a module and from the complete module. Two modules failed during the cycling due to a connecting error and/or temperature issues. It had turned out that the cycling temperature chosen first (45 °C) had been too large, thus, the security circuit frequently shut down the experiment. Temperature had been reduced afterwards to 35°C. Two modules could be cycled for around 500 cycles before the experiment had to be stopped at roughly SOH 90 since the end of the project run time had been reached. The EIS measurement conditions had been the same as mentioned in 3.1.

The figure on the left-hand side shows an exemplary spectrum of an individual cell in one of the modules. The blue spectrum is the originally measured one. The red data show the spectrum after pre-processing for DRT analysis (see D5). The spectrum on the right-hand side shows that of the corresponding module. The spectra of the individual cell are rather noisy because of the small impedance of the high energy cell. That of the complete module is rather smooth. As mentioned in the introduction, there has been just a preliminary, qualitative evaluation of the data for the reasons mentioned.

3.3 Other batteries

3.3.1 Extending the lower cut-off voltage down to 2.5 V

In this specific LCT (2.13) conducted at NIC four reference battery cells were cycled (with 4 A charge/discharge current and voltage hold at the upper cut-off voltage of 4.2 V) in the extended voltage range with lower cut-off voltage of 2.5 V and temperature of 23 °C. The evolution of SoH with cycle number is shown in **Fig. 33** where it is plotted together with the SoH evolution of the cells which were used to determine the effect of temperature on SoH and corresponding EIS.

Fig.32. Evolution of SoH with cycle number of the reference cells (NIC-13, NIC-14, NIC-17 and NIC-18) where the effect of extended voltage range (lower cut-off lowered to 2.5 V) was monitored. The evolutions are shown together with the cells from task where the effect of temperature during cycling was studied.

It can be clearly seen in **Fig. 32** that lowering the lower cut-off voltage from 3 V to 2.5 V extremely reduces the cycle life at 23 °C. In the voltage region between 3 V and 2.5 V there is a rather small additional capacity gained (at 4 A discharge about +3.5 % for pristine cell). Thus, the utilization of this initial additional capacity induces a very detrimental degradation scenario. Interestingly, after the initially rapid decrease of SoH at about 60 % of remaining SoH the cells seem to somewhat stabilize and further SoH reduction appears to be less rapid. The underlying physical processes behind this kind of behaviour are not known. In **Fig. 33** it is shown the corresponding SoH-IZI evolution to $f_{min} = 10$ mHz and EIS spectra measured at SoC = 100 %. When compared with the evolutions for the other cells where the effect of temperature during cycling was studied it can be seen that the extended voltage range with the lower cut-off voltage of 2.5 V results in the increased $-\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$ slope. As described above the $\Delta|Z|(10 \text{ mHz})$ increase is due to the increase of electrolyte resistance and increase of interfacial resistances – the latter usually being a prevailing contribution. Accordingly, the comparison of the SoH-EIS correlations in **Fig. 33** suggests that at the same SoH the largest increase of interfacial resistance is found for the cells cycled at 45 °C and the smallest for the cells cycled at 5 °C. The cells cycled down to 2.5 V at 23 °C show smaller increase in the interfacial resistance compared to the cells cycled down to 3 V at same temperature.

Fig. 33. SoH-IZI correlation for 4 reference cells cycled within extended voltage range with lower cut-off voltage of 2.5 V and at 23 °C. The impedance magnitudes IZI correspond to $f_{min} = 10$ mHz for the spectra measured at SoC = 100 %. The evolutions are shown together with the cells from task where the effect of temperature during cycling was studied.

The results shown in **Fig. 33** one more time confirm that impedance-based SoH-IZI correlation analysis provides a useful tool for following of the internal state of Lithium ion batteries.

3.3.2 Cylindrical LFP-Graphite battery

Within the LCT task 2.14 performed at NIC cycling testing together with periodic measurements of EIS were conducted on two cylindrical LFP-Graphite battery cells (NIC-15, NIC-16) with nominal capacity of 3 Ah. The cells were cycled in galvanostatic mode with +2.85 A charge followed by voltage hold (current limit C/30) and -4.95 A discharge cycling in the voltage range of 2 V - 3.6 V at 24 °C. Periodic evaluation of SoH was performed by measuring discharge capacity in galvanostatic cycle with applied current of +/- 0.4 A and with voltage hold at the upper cut-off voltage (3.6 V, current limit C/30). Periodic measurement of EIS was performed at 6 selected SoC's (in a similar manner as in all the other LCTs). The evolution of SoH with cycle number is shown in **Fig. 34** where it is plotted together with the SoH evolution of some selected sets of NMC-Graphite cells at comparable cycling conditions. It is evident from **Fig. 34** that the LFP-based battery cells exhibit superior cycling (SoH) stability compared to the batteries with 811-NMC cathode. The initial loss of SoH for the LFP-based cells in the first stage of cycling is much smaller compared to the 811-NMC-based. Moreover, in the second stage of cycling the LFP-based cells show very small rate of $-\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$ decrease of about -0.15% per 100 cycles – compared to found about -1% per 100 cycles for 811-NMC-based cells. In fact, the LFP-based cells do not enter into the third stage cycling even after 5000 cycles.

Fig. 34. Evolution of SoH with cycle number of the two LFP-Graphite cells (NIC-15, NIC-16) cycled at 24 °C. The evolutions are shown together with evolution of some selected sets of NMC-Graphite cells at comparable cycling conditions.

The superior cycling stability of the LFP-based cells is expectedly reflected in the corresponding SoH- $|Z|$ correlations shown in **Fig. 35** and **Fig. 36**. There is striking difference between the evolution of SoH- $|Z|$ correlations when comparing reference NMC-based cell and the LFP-based cells. For example, the two NMC-based cells tested at JRC at 35 °C (JRC-10 and JRC-11) that were cycled beyond 5000 cycles showed large increase of $|Z|$ compared to the pristine state, final $|Z|$ being larger than 150 m Ω . Somewhat smaller $|Z|$ could be anticipated at 5000 cycles from the extrapolation of the data for the NMC-based cells cycled at 23 °C (in the range of about 125 m Ω). On the contrary, the LFP-based cells showed negligible impedance growth (during the initial 100 cycles $|Z|$ was even decreasing).

Fig. 35. Comparison of SoH- $|Z|$ correlations of LFP-based cells (SoC = 50%) and 811-NMC-based cells (SoC = 100%) cycled at comparable cycling conditions. The impedance magnitudes $|Z|$ correspond to $f_{min} = 10$ mHz.

Thus, one more time we found that the cycling (SoH) stability is directly reflected in the corresponding impedance evolution. The change of impedance magnitude for NMC-based cells is large due to continuous and severe degradation processes taking place during long-term cycling. On the other hand, LFP-based cells are intrinsically more stable due to very stable structure of LFP active material that additionally exhibits superior chemical stability compared to Ni-rich NMC cathode materials. Moreover, the operating voltage range of LFP cathode is within the electrochemical stability window of electrolytes. Consequently, in non-severe operating conditions the progression of the degradation processes in LFP-Graphite cells at room temperature is very slow. This low degradation tendency was observed as very slow increase of $|Z|$ during cycling of the two tested LFP-based batteries.

Fig. 36. Enlarged part of comparison of SoH- $|Z|$ correlations of LFP-based cells (SoC = 50%) and 811-NMC-based cells (SoC = 100%) at high values of SoH.

4 Summary and outlook

4.1 Summary

Within WP2 all of the most important planned experimental LCT tasks on cells were eventually successfully finalized despite the intermittent Covid-19 pandemic related situation that for some of the included institutions partially reduced the accessibility to the laboratories. In particular, the number of 5 LCT stated in Annex 1 has been exceeded by far. On the other hand, several of the additional LCTs were cancelled mostly due to the need to compensate for the Covid-19 pandemic related loss of measurement time. Nevertheless, the realization of the major (and at the same time experimentally the most extensive) LCTs enabled accomplishment of all the main project activities in WP2 and closely related WP3. Accordingly, the joint measurement effort of all the partners produced strikingly large data sets of obtained impedance as well as NFR data. For illustration, merely the Inter-lab comparison LCT task on reference high-energy 811 NMC-Graphite battery cell produced more than 2100 EIS and about 300 NFR spectra. For example, the total number of all obtained (EIS and NFR) spectra on reference 18650 cells was over 5700.

We demonstrate in the present deliverable that for the case of the reference NMC-Graphite cell the standard capacity-based SoH vs. cycle number evolution often does not provide enough insight to distinguish between the role of test-condition-based impact and individual cell-to-cell variations on the output long-term cycling performance. In order to check repeatability of the LCTs at different institutions (with different measurement equipment) we introduced a simple methodology based on the so-called *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption*. The latter allows for the large experimental data sets of SoH and corresponding EIS evolutions to be simply analyzed by finding direct SoH-EIS correlation. Results of the applied SoH-EIS correlation analysis performed on the data obtained during tests of reference cells gave important insights that can be summarized as follows.

We found that SoH-IZI dependencies of reference cell during long-term cycling for minimal measured frequency $f_{min} = 10$ mHz of the impedance response often exhibit in a large cycle number range a close-to linear relationships. This is a very important observation since it directly supports the validity of the correlation analysis methodology based on the *minimal-frequency-impedance assumption*. Moreover, it could potentially provide additional insights into the degradation mechanisms taking place in this type of battery cells. In the Inter-lab comparison task we observed that both – the SoH with cycle number as well as the corresponding SoH- $|Z|$ evolution exhibit 3 distinct stages. In the first stage of cycling a rather fast decrease of SoH was observed that could probably be related to the rapid initial degradation of Silicon particles in the anode. In the second stage of cycling we observed that the close-to-linear rate of SoH decrease with cycle number is aligned with a close-to-linear rate of SoH decrease with increase in impedance magnitude, $|Z|$. Accordingly, we were able to relate the observed $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta\text{Cycle}$ rate with $\Delta\text{SoH}/\Delta|Z|$ rate. We found that for the reference cells in the SoH range between 0.7 and ~0.9 that in the average there was about 6 m Ω increase in $|Z|$ per 100 cycles (for the selected SoC = 100%, cycling at 45 °C).

The aging tests performed at elevated temperature of 45 °C showed practically linear increase of $|Z|$ (at 10 mHz) with duration of aging. The aging of reference cells at SoC = 80 % was more severe compared to the aging at SoC = 50 %, with the aging at SoC = 80 % producing roughly “equivalent degradation” of 1 % of initial SoH loss per 1 month of aging (storage). The actual damage to the cells during the aging tests should be directly experimentally verified.

One of the most distinct observations was found in the case of the LCTs where effect of temperature during cycling was monitored. Specifically, we found that there is a definite trend of SoH development with the cycling temperature: the lower the temperature the larger is the rate of the SoH-IZI decrease. Moreover, in some ranges the SoH-IZI dependencies are rather close to linear. The latter fact gives a direct affirmation that impedance-based techniques could indeed be used for monitoring and possibly even predicting of the future SoH evolution in the second use (“life”) of Lithium ion batteries.

The effect of DoD range during cycling showed complex relations which will have to be further studied more in detail in the future studies. Namely, it was not possible to unambiguously extract definite conclusions regarding the most preferred DoD range to achieve stable long term cycling. Moreover, it is not straightforward to obtain clear reasoning about the observed trends in the SoH-IZI correlations. Partially this is due to the fact that effect of DoD cycling range on stability is rather complex and furthermore it is additionally blurred by the individual cell-to-cell variations. Larger number of cells should be tested at the same testing condition. The latter would help to identify the “outliers” and enable selecting the group of cells that show repeatable behaviour.

Extending the usually used voltage range (3 V – 4.2 V) during cycling of reference cells by lowering the lower cut-off voltage from usual 3 V down to 2.5 V resulted in extremely reduced cycling stability.

Accordingly, SoH evolution with cycle number showed very fast decrease that consequently extensively shortened cycle life. The cells cycled down to 2.5 V at 23 °C showed smaller increase in the interfacial resistance compared to the cells cycled down to 3 V at same temperature and at the same SoH value.

Preliminary sets of measurements on LFP-Graphite battery cells showed (expected) superior cycling (SoH) stability compared to 811-NMC-based cells. The comparison of the SoH- $|Z|$ evolutions of these two types of cells showed that the intrinsically low degradation tendency of LFP-Graphite battery was directly observed as a very slow (and cumulatively small) increase of $|Z|$ during long-term cycling. These preliminary findings demonstrate striking difference between the degradation tendencies of 811-NMC and LFP active cathode materials in the corresponding battery systems with Graphite anode.

4.2 Conclusions and outlook

The systematic impedance measurements together with applied simple SoH-IZI correlation analysis provide direct confirmation that evolution of EIS spectra during the first application use (“life”) of high-energy NMC-Graphite Lithium-ion battery until reaching EoL (at SoH = 80 %) could in principle be utilized to predict the further evolution of SoH during the second use (“life”) of those types of batteries. The NFR measurements show good reproducibility from cell-to-cell variations even though no inter-lab comparison is possible due to the limitation in the measurement capacities of the institutions. Also, NFR results deliver a promising capability at distinguishing different aging stages. By analyzing the Y_2 and Y_3 signals, we can obtain key insights not only on the kinetic but also the symmetrical behaviour of the charge transfer process.

In future the efforts should be directed in checking whether these (EIS and NFR) observations hold true in general for various types of battery chemistries and furthermore to verify the extended validity of these observations in practical circumstances of real battery usage. For example, it will be important to study how the intermittent and dynamic usage of a Lithium ion battery is reflected in the SoH-EIS correlation. In addition, it will be of crucial importance to validate how the relations found in the individual-cell studies are translated on larger (compound) systems e.g. electric vehicle battery module/pack as well as large stationary battery storage power stations.

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